

WP4 Full integration & packaging of super-sensor

Leader: VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.

Super-Sensor Demonstrator

Nano volume DSS dispensing

Precise signal recording for Alzheimer's biomarker detection

SensApp

European project SensApp develops groundbreaking diagnostics for Alzheimer's disease – new sensor technology to enable diagnosis from a routine blood sample

Automated liquid handling

The super-sensor includes a Droplet-Split-and-Stack (DSS) dispenser integrating the electro-magnetic field actuation, sample slide actuation and precise alignment of disposable loading layer μ -Orifice.

Precise alignment

DSS dispenser unit includes a laptop with user-friendly control software.

The software includes automated system initialization steps to home the XYZ-motors and activate the heating system for LiNbO_3 crystal and the cameras for dispensing control.

Super sensitive detection requires a precise knowledge of the location of dispensed samples.

A custom calibration routine with a coordination plate has been designed to ensure the alignment precision from DSS unit to the Read-out Module.

DSS DISPENSER

Operator controlled dispensing

The DSS dispenser has automated functions and operator controlled steps.

The system has the flexibility for further automation after the dispensing routines have been fully developed.

The loading layer locking mechanism enables changing the disposable layer between patients easily.

The stability of the system ensures precision between sample slide changes.

The top-camera imaging enables dispensing quality control.

The side-camera imaging provides the operator with information on crystal contact to sample slide and dispensing process.

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DSS DISPENSER

Heating cycle for crystal activation

System integration and packaging of layers

Position calibration with top-view imaging

μ Orifice on top of pyro-stage

Automated functions to assist operator

READ-OUT MODULE

Automated laser scanning fluorescence detection

The super-sensor includes an automated Read-Out Module (ROM) for biomarker assay signal recording. The ROM detects the fluorescence signal excited with laser and detected by PMT sensor in confocal arrangement to suppress the background signal. The desired signal to noise ratio (SNR) is ensured with high NA aspheric optics. The signal is collected with spiral geometry scanning around the dispensed spot location with 100 μm illumination beam diameter and 200 μm detection area diameter. The confocal sensing sets extra requirements for position alignment and distance control from optics to the sample plane.

Precision for sensing

The ROM includes an inductive distance sensor, which scans the distance of sample slide edges to the optics and defines a 3D plane for the detection. There is an automated algorithm adjusting the distance for each sample spot and ensuring optimal signal collection. The InduSensor distance info is set using a custom calibration disc.

The XY positions for the sample spots are translated from the DSS dispenser to the ROM using the custom made coordination plate. The coordination plate can be used to check the laser and detection alignment as well as to position the detection points.

Fluorescence signal sensing and recording

The ROM includes a laptop with user-friendly control software. The software includes automated system initialization steps to home the XYZ-motors and activate the shutters for laser and PMT as well as activating the distance sensor (InduSensor).

The system allows both automated signal collection as well as manual control utilizing an imaging camera and blue LED illumination.

READ-OUT MODULE

Sample spot locations on reaction slide

Sample slide spiral scanning with XYZ motors

ROM alignment with laser, coordination plate and camera imaging

User-interface of the ROM control software

InduSensor for determination of sample slide orientation and distance control

COLLABORATION to reach the targets of the project demonstrator:

CNR development of DSS dispensing concept and assay development

VUB development of DSS disposable loading layer and read-out module signal collection

VTT DSS and read-out module prototype development, instrumentation and automation

GIN climate chamber concept and assay automation

DICMaPI simulations for μ Orifice development

JKU pyro-layer development

PULEJO clinical partner supporting assay development and end-user of the instrument

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